

rated from vanadate, ferricyanide, thiocyanate, bromate, permanganate, etc. having of lower K_a values. The selectivity scale for B_1 at pH 3.0–3.5 was found to be $BrO_3^- < IO_3^-; SCN^- < [Fe(CN)]_6^{3-} < [Fe(CN)]_6^{4-}; MnO_4^- < VO_3^- < AsO_4^{3-} < AsO_3^{3-} < CrO_4^{2-} < PO_4^{3-}$. At higher pH, CrO_4^{2-} was more selective than PO_4^{3-} for B_3 .

Ion-exchange separation: Taking advantage of the differences in K_a values the following separations have been achieved (specific eluate volumes are given in the parenthesis): thiocyanate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5) from chromate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$), phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$), vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$), ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 $M H_2SO_4$), arsenite (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$) and iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$); chromate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$) from permanganate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5), ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 $M H_2SO_4$), bromate (20 ml of dilute HCl , pH 3.5), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$), phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$), and vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$); ferricyanide (20 ml of dilute HCl , pH 3.5) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 $M H_2SO_4$), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$), phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$), chromate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$), vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$); permanganate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5) from iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$) and vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$); bromate (20 ml of dilute H_2SO_4 , pH 3.5) from phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$) and arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 $M H_2SO_4$); vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 $M H_2SO_4$) and phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$); and oxalate (25 ml of 0.0025 $M H_2SO_4$ in 0.5 $M Na_2SO_4$) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 $M H_2SO_4$) and phosphate (25 ml of 1 $M H_2SO_4$).

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One-step Synthesis of Steroidal Lactams from Ketones of Spirostane Series

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THE Beckmann rearrangement of steroidal ketoximes and Schmidt reaction of steroidal ketones are the usual methods to obtain steroidal lactams¹. Olah and Fung² reported the synthesis of lactams in one-step from alicyclic ketones by the action of hydroxylamine-*O*-sulphonic acid (HOSA) in hot formic acid. We now report the formation of lactams from steroidal ketones of spirostane series by the aforesaid method.

(25*R*)-5-Spirosten-3 β -ol (diosgenin; **1a**) on reaction with thionyl chloride in benzene solution at room temperature afforded 3 β -chloro-(25*R*)-5-spirostene (**1b**). The reduction of **1b** with sodium in isopentanol furnished (25*R*)-5-spirostene (**1c**). The chromic acid oxidation of **1b** and **1c** in glacial acetic acid after usual workup afforded their respective α,β -unsaturated ketones (**2b** and **2a**). The α,β -unsaturated ketone (**2c**) was prepared according to the method by Singh and Padmanabhan³.

The steroidal ketones (**2a–c**) were subjected to the action of HOSA in hot formic acid (60–70°) in the nitrogen atmosphere for 2 h and after usual workup the lactams (**3a–c**) were obtained in good yields (60%). However, if reaction with the same reagent (HOSA) was carried out at room temperature for 30 min in an atmosphere of nitrogen it gave the respective intermediate oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (**2d–f**). The oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (**2d–f**) on keeping over a column of neutral alumina followed by chromatography (Craig's procedure⁴) afforded the lactams (**3a–c**).

The lactams (**3a–c**) were also prepared by the Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes (**2g–i**) using *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (PTS) in pyridine to form oxime tosylates, which on keeping over a column of neutral alumina followed by chromatography⁵ gave the lactams (**3a–c**). The lactams obtained by the above two methods are identical in all respects (ir, m m.p. and co-tlc). Their spectral data are comparable with that of (25*R*)-7 α -aza-7-oxo-*B*-homo-5-spirosten-3 β -yl acetate^{3,4}.

The lactam (**3a**) on catalytic hydrogenation using Pd/C in absolute methanol gave the saturated lactam (**4**); tlc in benzene–ether (1:2) showed single spot; ν_{max} 3 200 (NH) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 5.5 (1H, s, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.5 (1H, m, 8 β -H) and 1.6 ($C_{10}-CH_3$); λ_{max} 240 nm.

The analytical and physical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % · Found/(Calcd.)		
			O	H	N
1b	148–50	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ O ₁₀	75.0 (75.6)	9.49 (9.6)	—
1c	168–70	C ₂₇ H ₄₃ O ₈	81.6 (81.9)	9.9 (10.1)	—
2a	190–92	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ O ₈	78.6 (78.9)	9.7 (9.9)	—
2b	138–40	C ₂₇ H ₃₉ O ₁₀	72.64 (72.8)	8.74 (8.9)	—
2d	205–206	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ NO ₈ S	68.21 (68.4)	8.63 (8.9)	2.94 (3.0)
2e	152–54	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ ClNO ₈ S	63.65 (63.8)	7.85 (7.9)	2.75 (2.9)
2g	168–69	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ NO ₈	75.87 (76.0)	9.6 (9.8)	3.27 (3.4)
2h	157–58	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ NO ₁₀	70.28 (70.4)	8.67 (8.8)	3.03 (3.07)
3a	220–22	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ NO ₈	75.87 (75.95)	9.6 (9.8)	3.27 (3.4)
3b	171–73	C ₂₇ H ₄₀ NO ₁₀	70.28 (70.3)	8.67 (8.9)	3.03 (3.07)
4	198–200	C ₂₇ H ₄₃ NO ₈	75.52 (75.7)	10.02 (10.05)	3.26 (3.4)

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, uv spectra (95% methanol) on a Beckmann DUz spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard. Petroleum ether refers to a fraction of b.p. 60–80°.

3β-Chloro-(25R)-5-spirostene (1b): To diosgenin (**1a**; 10 g) dissolved in benzene (40 ml) was added freshly distilled thionyl chloride (7.5 ml) with cooling. After the vigorous reaction subsided the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 15 min with occasional stirring. The reaction mixture was then poured on ice-cold water. The organic layer separated was washed successively with sodium carbonate (5%) and water and dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous). The removal of the solvent gave a solid which was recrystallised from acetone–methanol as white crystals (**1b**); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 620 (C=O) and 760 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

(25R)-5-spirostene (1c): To **1b** (10 g) was added isopentanol (230 ml) and the mixture heated to 60–70° and gradually added pieces of sodium (20 g). The heating was continued until sodium pieces were dissolved completely. The reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water and neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid. The alcoholic layer was separated and concentrated under reduced pressure to obtain a solid which was recrystallised from acetone–methanol (**1c**); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

α , β -Unsaturated ketones (**2a**, **2b**) from steroidal cycloalkenes (**1c**, **1b**). A typical experiment: To a well stirred solution of **1b** or **1c** (5.4 g) in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) a solution of chromium trioxide (4 g in 10 ml of 50% AcOH) was added dropwise during 2 h at 75–80° and further stirring was continued for 2 h at the same temperature. The excess of chromium trioxide was then destroyed by adding methanol (10 ml) and acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure to obtain a dark coloured semi-solid. It was extracted with benzene and the benzene layer was washed successively with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, dilute hydrochloric acid and finally with water. The dried benzene extract on removal of the solvent under reduced pressure afforded the α , β -unsaturated ketones (**2b** or **2a**), which were recrystallised from ethanol as colourless needles.

Reaction of HOSA in formic acid on the α , β -unsaturated ketones (2a–c) to obtain the lactams (3a–c): (i) To a solution of **2a–c** (2 g) in formic acid (98%, 20 ml) a solution of HOSA in formic acid (0.4 g, in 10 ml) was added dropwise. The mixture was heated at 60–70° for 2 h and then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting semi-solid was extracted with benzene and after the usual work-up it gave the respective lactams (**3a–c**; 1.2 g, 60%) which were recrystallised from ether–methanol.

(ii) To a solution of **2a–c** (2 g) in formic acid (98%, 20 ml) was added HOSA (0.5 g) at room temperature for 10 min and left it at room temperature (30°) for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water and extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with 5% NaHCO₃, dilute HCl and water and dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous). The removal of the solvent gave the intermediate oxime-O-sulphonic acids (**2d–f**; 1.6 g, 80%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400 (OH), 1 630 (C=N)

and 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$). The above oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (1 g) were then kept over neutral alumina (30 g) for 1 h and subjected to chromatography. The eluates from benzene-ether (1 : 1) gave the lactams (3a-c); ν_{max} 3 180 (NH), 1 670, 1 615 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CONH}$); λ_{max} 220 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1) (α,β -unsaturated lactam⁶); δ 6.25 (1H, s, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 5.6 (vinyl-H), 3.5 (1H, m, $8\beta\text{-H}$); 3b and 3c δ 4.5 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, $3\alpha\text{-H}$)⁷.

The ketoximes (2g-i) from the ketones (2a-c) : To a solution of 2a-c (1.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.5 g) and sodium acetate (5 g) were added and refluxed for 4 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the remaining solution was poured in ice-cold water to obtain the oxime (2g-i; 1.2 g, 80%) which was recrystallised from ethanol.

Beckmann rearrangement of the ketoximes (2g-i) : To a solution of the ketoxime (2g-i; 1 g) in dry pyridine (15 ml), PTS (1 g) was added and kept at room temperature (30°) for 12 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in ice-cold water to obtain a solid (oxime tosylates). The solid was extracted with ether- CHCl_3 mixture (1 : 1) and the extract was washed with dilute HCl and water and dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous). The removal of solvent yielded light brown semi-solid, which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (30 g, Brockmann grade 1). Elution with petroleum-ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave the lactams (3a-c).

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Reaction of Lead(IV) Acetate with Steroidal Epoxides

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IN continuation of our previous studies¹⁻³ on the reactions of lead(IV) acetate with steroidal compounds, we carried out the reaction of lead(IV)

acetate with 5,6 α -oxido-5 α -cholestane (1) and its 3 β -substituted analogues (2-4), which provided hydroxy acetates and diacetates (5-9). The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of spectral evidences. The compounds are useful for comparative chemical studies of steroidal compounds as derivatives.

The epoxide (1)⁴ in acetic acid when treated with lead(IV) acetate provided the hydroxyacetate (5) and the diacetate (6) : *cholestan-5 α -hydroxy-6 β -acetate* (5; 30%) m.p. 104° (Found : C, 81.88; H, 11.01. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_3$ requires : C, 81.9; H, 11.0%); ν_{max} 3 450 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 4.5 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$ $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0 (3H, s, acetate protons), 1.1 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.75 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.90 and 0.85 (other methyl protons); *cholestan-5 α ,6 β -diacetate* (6; 20%), m.p. 150° (Found : C, 76.25; H, 10.65. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_4$ requires : C, 76.3; H, 11.0%); ν_{max} 3 420 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735, 1 730 ($2\times\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 4.6 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$ $W_{1/2}$ 9 Hz), 2.0, 1.9 ($2\times$ 3H, s, acetate protons), 1.1 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions the epoxides 2⁵ and 3-4⁶ provided 7-8 and 9-10, respectively. It is pertinent to mention that the epoxides 3 and 4 provided the same products 9⁸ and 10⁹ : *3 β -chloro-5 α -hydroxycholest-6 β -acetate*⁸ (7; 30%), m.p. 137° (Found : C, 72.42; H, 10.19. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 72.4; H, 10.2%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 3 450 (br, 3°-OH), 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 460 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ 5.4 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0 (3H, s, acetate protons), 1.28 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 (3H, s, $\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons); *3 β -chloro-5 α ,6 β -diacetate*⁸ (8; 22.5%), m.p. 112° (Found : C, 71.49; H, 9.92. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{45}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 71.4; H, 9.9%); positive Beilstein test; ν_{max} 1 740, 1 735 ($2\times\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$), 1 460, 1 050 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 760 cm^{-1} (CCl_4); δ 4.75 (mc, $\text{C}_6\text{-}\alpha\text{H}$, $W_{1/2}$ 8 Hz), 2.0, 1.9 ($2\times$ 3H, s, acetate protons), 1.28 ($\text{C}_{10}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.68 ($\text{C}_{13}\text{-CH}_3$), 0.92 and 0.80 (other methyl protons); *3 β -5 α -diacetoxy-6 β -hydroxycholestane*⁹ (9; 25%), m.p. 96° (Found : C, 73.80; H, 10.32. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{53}\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 73.8;